

FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH BEHAVIOR OF A RANDOM FIBER SHEET MOLDING COMPOUND COMPOSITE

D. R. Atodaria¹, S. K. Putatunda¹ and P. K. Mallick²

¹ *Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Wayne State University,
Detroit, Michigan 48202, USA*

² *Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Michigan-Dearborn,
Dearborn, Michigan 48128, USA*

SUMMARY: The purpose of this study is to investigate the fatigue crack growth behavior of a random fiber sheet molding compound (SMC-R) composite and to examine the applicability of a new fatigue crack growth rate model to this material. In this study, the fatigue crack growth rate of SMC-R was measured using a compliance approach. The new fatigue crack growth rate model is based on a power law equation and takes into account not only the effect of the stress intensity factor range, but also the effect of crack growth at various stages of loading using a weight average stress intensity factor. It was observed that this new model can represent the fatigue crack growth rate of this SMC-R at three different load ratios in a single unifying curve.

KEYWORDS: random fiber composites, sheet molding compounds, fatigue crack growth, compliance, power law equation

INTRODUCTION

Randomly oriented short fiber reinforced sheet molding compound (SMC-R) composites are finding increasing use in many structural applications, including automotive structures and bridge structures. Many of these structures experience repeated loading in service and fatigue failure must be considered as one of the critical failure modes in their design. Use of SMC in these structures requires that a better understanding of the fatigue failure process and a suitable fatigue life prediction technique be developed for this class of composite materials.

There is now a significant number of publications on the fatigue behavior of continuous fiber reinforced laminated composites; however, publications on the fatigue behavior of random fiber composites are extremely limited. In an earlier work [1], we proposed a new empirical model to characterize the fatigue crack growth behavior of random fiber composites. In the present work, we have studied the fatigue crack growth rate of a random fiber SMC composite at three different load ratios and extended the application of our model to the fatigue life prediction of this material.

PROPOSED MODEL

An understanding of fatigue behavior is important for any material that experiences repeated loading during service. There are basically two approaches for generating information and knowledge of the fatigue behavior of materials: (1) the S-N curve or the ϵ -N curve approach, and (2) the fracture mechanics approach. The fracture mechanics approach assumes the presence of inherent cracks or flaws in the material and attempts to predict its life using empirical models of fatigue crack growth rate. The most commonly used Mode I fatigue crack growth rate model is based on the Paris power law equation [2]

$$\frac{da}{dN} = A(\Delta K)^m \quad (1)$$

where, da/dN = fatigue crack growth rate

ΔK = difference in the maximum and minimum Mode I stress intensity factors

A, m = curve-fitted power law constants for the material

Eqn. (1) has been used extensively for metals and to some extent, with composite materials as well. Wang et. al. [3] employed Eqn. (1) to establish fatigue crack growth rate in an SMC. They found the value of A and m to be 7.58×10^{-8} and 9.65, respectively. Similar attempts have also been made to fit Eqn. (1) to fatigue crack growth rate of other random fiber composites, such as injection molded thermoplastic composites [4].

The Paris model, given by Eqn. (1), assumes that the fatigue crack growth rate depends only on the stress intensity factor range, ΔK . For a fatigue test with zero load ratio, $K = K_{max}$, and thus, according to Eqn. (1), the fatigue crack growth rate depends only on K_{max} , regardless of the mean load imposed during cycling. Furthermore, for any given value of stress intensity factor range, the fatigue crack growth rate is independent of other values of K within this range. For many composites, it is observed that crack growth occurs at stress levels that are lower than the maximum stress imposed in the fatigue cycle and, therefore, stress intensity factors lower than the K_{max} will also have some effect on the fatigue crack growth rate of such composites. In each cycle, the crack may grow in a very slow and progressive manner as the stress increases from the minimum to the maximum value; however, the extent of damage growth may not be equal at each stress level. It is expected that the crack growth rate will be slower at low stress levels and will be faster as the stress increases toward the maximum value. Based on this assumption, we have proposed a modified power law model which takes into account this progressive crack propagation process by including a weight average value of K in addition to the stress intensity range that is already present in the Paris model. According to this modified model, the fatigue crack growth rate can be expressed as

$$\frac{da}{dN} = A_0 (\Delta K^\alpha \cdot K_{average}^\beta)^\gamma \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where, } K_{average} = \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{K_{th}}^{K_{max}} K^w \right]^{1/w}$$

n = number of divisions by which the range of K_{th} to K_{max} is equally divided (Fig. 1)

w = weighting factor

$A_0, \alpha, \beta, \gamma$ = constants

K_{th} = threshold stress intensity factor below which no crack propagation occurs

Note that the constants A_0 , α , β , γ and the weighting factor w are determined by iteration to fit the experimental data. In Ref. 1, we assumed $\alpha = \beta = 0.5$ and found that Eqn. (2) fits the experimental data for random carbon fiber reinforced PEEK with $A_0 = 5.43 \times 10^{-20}$, $w = 16.9$ and $\gamma = 17.4$. The powers α and β may not have the same value, since, depending on the material, ΔK and K_{average} may have different influences on the fatigue crack growth rate of the material.

Fig. 1: Partition from K_{th} to K_{max} in 'n' divisions for calculating $K_{average}$

In the present work, we have used the proposed model for a random fiber sheet molding compound composite. However, unlike the carbon fiber reinforced PEEK, the fatigue failure does not occur by the enlargement of a single visible crack. In the first few fatigue tests performed with SMC specimens, it was observed that the fatigue crack in this material does not follow a well defined path. As the fatigue loading is continued, a number of small cracks appear in the vicinity of the original notch tip. These cracks are oriented at different angles with the notch plane. With a traveling microscope focused on the specimen surfaces, the opening and closing of these cracks can be clearly seen; however it was difficult to judge whether these cracks are only at the surfaces or also extend deep into the thickness of the specimen. Eventually one of these cracks extends in length, but stops after a slight extension. With continued cycling, multiple small cracks appear in the vicinity of the extended crack and the whole process of stop-and-go crack growth process is repeated. Another point to note is that the crack extension occurs in SMC in a zigzag manner, often deviating from the plane of the original notch. This created a problem in that the crack length could not be accurately measured during the fatigue test. This has led us to use the increase in specimen compliance as an indirect measure of the fatigue crack growth in SMC. The compliance measurement technique is described in the next section.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material used in this study is a sheet molding compound (SMC) composite containing 25 mm long chopped E-glass fibers randomly oriented in a thermosetting polyester resin. The fiber weight fraction is estimated to be 30 percent. In addition to the randomly oriented fibers and the matrix, the other major ingredient in the material is a calcium carbonate filler which is randomly dispersed in the matrix. The nominal thickness of compression molded SMC plate was 3.6 mm.

The fatigue experiments were conducted in an MTS servohydraulic testing machine using a 18 kN load cell cartridge. Compact tension specimens with the dimensions shown in Fig. 2 were used in all fatigue tests. The crack opening displacement during the fatigue tests were measured using a clip gauge, which was inserted at the notch mouth in the beginning of each test. Fatigue cycling was performed in a load-controlled mode at room temperature using a frequency of 2 Hz. Three different load ratios, P_{\min}/P_{\max} , were used, namely 0.1, 0.3 and 0.5.

Fig. 2: Compact tension specimen

In order to use the compliance measurement as an indirect measure of fatigue crack growth, we had to first establish a compliance calibration equation which relates the specimen compliance to an equivalent crack length. The calibration curve was obtained using 10 specimens with different initial notch lengths, varying in length from 12 to 20 mm. Each of these specimens was cycled once between 0.67 kN and 1.33 kN at 0.1 Hz. The specimen compliance, defined as the ratio of crack opening displacement (COD) to load, is determined from the loading portion of the load vs. COD diagram obtained during this test.

The specimen compliance during the fatigue test was measured at regular intervals. Instead of applying the full load in the first cycle, the load was increased in steps. After reaching the end of each load step, the specimen was allowed to fatigue for a few cycles at 2 Hz. before recording the hysteresis loop depicting the load vs. the crack opening displacement at 0.1 Hz. The load was then increased to the next step. This process was continued until the full load

was reached and the specimen was subsequently allowed to cycle between the maximum and minimum loads for the duration of its life. The specimen compliance was calculated from the digital data of load and crack opening displacement using the Excel software. A function called ‘linest’ in the Excel software was used in to calculating the slope of the loading portion of the hysteresis loop.

RESULTS

The compliance calibration diagram for the SMC material considered is shown in Fig. 3. Following equation was obtained relating the compliance to the crack length :

$$C = 5.903 \times 10^{-7} a^{1.276} \tag{3}$$

Fig. 3: Compliance Calibration Diagram for Estimating Fatigue Crack Length

The stress intensity factor for the compact tension specimen was calculated using the following equation [5]:

$$K = \frac{P}{B \sqrt{W}} f \left(\frac{a}{W} \right) \tag{4}$$

where, P = applied load on the specimen, B = specimen thickness,
 W = width of the specimen from the center of the loading point,
 a = crack length measured from the center of the loading point, and
 for a compact tension specimen,

$$f\left(\frac{a}{W}\right) = \frac{2 + \frac{a}{W}}{\left(1 - \frac{a}{W}\right)^{3/2}} \left[0.886 + 4.64\left(\frac{a}{W}\right) - 13.32\left(\frac{a}{W}\right)^2 + 14.72\left(\frac{a}{W}\right)^3 - 5.60\left(\frac{a}{W}\right)^4 \right]$$

Fig. 4 : Fatigue crack growth rate vs. ΔK

Fig. 4 shows the fatigue crack growth rate vs. ΔK for three different load ratios considered in this study. This figure shows that the fatigue crack growth rate of the SMC increases with increasing load ratio. If the Paris equation is used to model the fatigue crack growth rate, there will be different constants for different load ratios. Similar observation can be made if the fatigue crack growth rate is plotted as a function of K_{average} (Fig. 5); however, the distinction between the load ratios is much narrower in this figure. Next, the effects of K and K_{average} are combined using different values of α and β for the powers of these two parameters, and as shown in Fig. 6, the fatigue crack growth data for all three load ratios fall in a very narrow band for $\alpha = 0.15$ and $\beta = 0.85$. This indicates that Eqn. (2) can be used to unify the load ratio effect in the SMC. The best fit line drawn through the data points for all three load ratios has the equation given by

$$\frac{da}{dN} = 2.06 \times 10^{-20} (\Delta K^{0.15} K_{\text{average}}^{0.85})^{11.2} \quad (5)$$

The experimental fatigue crack growth rate for each load ratio was compared with the fatigue crack growth rate predicted by Eqn. (5). One such comparison is shown in Fig. 7 for load ratio $R=0.1$. As can be seen in Fig. 7, there is a close agreement between the experimentally

determined values and predicted values. Similar agreement was also observed for the other two load ratios.

Fig. 5 : Fatigue Crack Growth Rate vs. $K_{average}$

Fig. 6 : Fatigue crack growth rate vs. combined ΔK & $K_{average}$ as per model

Fig. 7 : Comparison of experimental fatigue crack growth rate with the one predicted by model

CONCLUSIONS

1. The compliance measurement approach was shown to be an effective method for monitoring the fatigue crack growth in random fiber SMC composites.
2. The proposed model is capable of unifying the fatigue crack growth rate at three load ratios considered into a single power law equation:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = 2.06 \times 10^{-20} (\Delta K^{0.15} K_{\text{average}}^{0.85})^{11.2}$$

3. Good agreement was found between predicted fatigue crack growth rate using the proposed model and the experimentally measured fatigue crack growth rate in a random fiber SMC composite.

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